

CUES

CONSUMERS' UNDERSTANDING OF EATING SUSTAINABLY

D 3.1 Communication Toolkit

Empowering Consumers Through Food Industry Change: Strategic Value of Transparency

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Executive Summary

This document presents Deliverable 3.1 of the EU CUES project, which aims to empower consumers to make more sustainable food choices by supporting change at cultural, industry, and policy levels. At the industry level, the EU CUES project equips actors in the food value chain with tools and strategies to enhance their transparency, traceability, and trustworthiness to promote sustainable food options for consumers.

The Communication Toolkit is a practical guide for food value chain actors on how to create and capture value through transparency across the food value chain. It is grounded in the dynamic capability framework (Teece, 2018) and draws on desk research and a multi-actor participatory approach, including eight co-identification and co-creation workshops held in Italy (TCA), Greece (KEPKA), Iceland (LOKI Foods) and Hungary (KLT) during 2024 and 2025. These activities resulted in creating the Toolkit into three sections: “Awareness”, “Action”, and “Aspiration”. The “Awareness” section explains the strategic value of transparency and how it creates value for individual food value chain actors as well as for the wider food value chain. The “Action” section presents the intervention Scenarios identified through the co-creation workshops, organised into three context-based pathways: one for short food value chains (Scenario A), one for collective branding in large food manufacturing firms (Scenario B), and one focused on the empowerment of smallholders (Scenario C). It also provides a step-by-step guide to implementation, highlighting digital communication solutions that strengthen transparency and trustworthiness within food value chain Business Models. The “Aspiration” section focuses on considerations for scaling up interventions, describing how actors can sustain and expand impact once an intervention and its digital tools become part of everyday operations.

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List of Terms and Definitions

Table 1: Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
Business Model	an architecture for how a firm creates and delivers value to customers and the mechanisms
intervention	a process of integrating a technological innovation into the Business Model
digital tool	a digital means of transmitting information
Scenario	a context-specific framework for an intervention
Causal Loop Diagram	a visual tool for mental modelling, helping to explicitly map the understanding of the problem and making it transparent and visible for others
Value Network Map	a visual tool that helps in getting a grip on systems by mapping how values connect
Ecosystem Pie Model	a tool that enables the qualitative mapping, analysis and design of innovation ecosystems

List of Abbreviations

Table 2: List of Abbreviations

Term	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
B2G	Business-to-Government
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CLD	Causal Loop Diagram
CUES	Consumers' Understanding of Eating Sustainably
EPM	Ecosystem Pie Model
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GMO	Genetically modified organism
ISO	International Organization for Standardization

MS	milestone
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
SAFA	Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture Systems
VNM	Value Network Map
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1 About this Communication Toolkit

Transparency is essential for empowering consumers to make informed, conscious (Nuwarapaksha et al., 2024) and sustainable (Liu et al., 2023) food choices. Consumers increasingly perceive transparency not merely as the provision of information, but as a catalyst for change, with social and environmental sustainability emerging as key motivators for their food decisions.

As consumer expectations continue to rise, the standards defining transparency have become more rigorous for stakeholders within the food value chain (Astill et al., 2023). Initially, transparency was characterised as a process of information disclosure, primarily linked to corporate accountability (Eijffinger & Geraats, 2006). Over time, it has evolved into a multidimensional construct that fosters trust not only between businesses and consumers but also among businesses themselves. Therefore, for transparency to be effective, information must be accessible, accurate, clearly presented, and delivered in a timely manner (Schnackenberg & Tomlinson, 2016).

This Communication Toolkit addresses the necessity for a deeper investigation into how to create and capture value through transparency efforts. It serves as a practical guide for stakeholders in the food value chain who aim to enhance transparency throughout the entire food value chain.

Inspired by the dynamic capability framework (Teece, 2018), this research applied desk research along with a multi-actor participatory approach. It includes eight co-identification and co-creation workshops conducted in Italy (TCA), Greece (KEPKA), Iceland (LOKI Foods), and Hungary (KLT) during 2024 and 2025.

In these workshops, a diverse range of food value chain actors were present, including food producers, food processors, food authorities, farmer cooperatives, policymakers, certification bodies, retailers, marketing agencies, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and open market vendors.

Considering the local context, each team outlined the barriers to transparency and the weaknesses of the existing food value chains (MS5). In the co-creation workshops, each team formulated a shared promise outlining the desired development path (actors and actions) to create and capture value through transparency efforts in food value chains.

This enabled the research team, with support from the technology provider FINT, to design **three context-based intervention Scenarios**. For each Scenario, the circumstances and context to which it applies, what it enables, and the strategic considerations are outlined. Moreover, a detailed 3-step **implementation pathway** is provided to achieve the desired Scenario, using a **digital tool** tailored to the Scenario's needs. This Communication Toolkit presents a concise explanation of:

STRATEGIC VALUE OF TRANSPARENCY

How and why is transparency a value for both individual food value chain actors and for the food value chain?

SCENARIOS FOR INTERVENTIONS TO ENABLE TRANSPARENCY

What scenarios are desirable to modern industry actors, according to the co-creation workshop results?

STEP-BY-STEP GUIDE TO IMPLEMENTING INTERVENTIONS

What pathways lead to these desirable scenarios? What digital tools can enhance transparency, traceability and trustworthiness in communicating food sustainability?

CONSIDERATIONS FOR SCALING-UP INTERVENTIONS

How do food value chain actors continue once an intervention is implemented and a digital tool is part of everyday operations?

1.2 Methodology

Deliverable D3.1 (Communication Toolkit) is grounded in the multi-actor participatory approach described in the Grant Agreement and operationalised in Task 3.1 (M6–M24) through a two-cycle workshop design that connects problem diagnosis with intervention co-design. Following a Participatory Action Research logic, stakeholders from food value chains were engaged as active contributors across both cycles, allowing insights and interventions to be developed iteratively through collective reflection and action. In line with this approach, WP3 followed a two-cycle structure:

CYCLE 1 (2024, CO-IDENTIFICATION)

Four workshops in Italy (TCA), Greece (KEPKA), Iceland (LOKI Foods), and Hungary (KLT) with stakeholders from the food value chain to surface and prioritise barriers and their underlying drivers across the value chain.

CYCLE 2 (2025, CO-CREATION)

Four workshops in the same countries and relatively similar workshop participants to translate the Cycle 1 barrier insights into collectively designed intervention directions, structured around shared commitments, partner roles, resources and coordinated activities.

1.2.1 Cycle 1 (2024): Co-Identification Workshop

Cycle 1 aimed to identify challenges, barriers, and influencing factors affecting transparency, traceability, and trustworthiness in value chain Business Models from the perspectives of diverse stakeholders. The workshop protocol was designed to support structured yet open discussion, allowing participants to articulate practical experiences while collectively exploring how barriers emerge, why they persist, and how they affect other actors and practices across the value chain. Collaborative visual mapping was used to externalise individual inputs into a shared space, enabling comparison of perspectives, pattern recognition, and the development of shared understandings.

Task 3.1 specifies the use of Causal Loop Diagrams (CLDs), Cycle 1 workshops did not require participants to construct formal CLD representations during the workshop. Instead, CLD logic was embedded implicitly in both workshop design and analysis by encouraging causal reasoning and system-level reflection. Facilitation prompts guided participants from identifying barriers toward discussing underlying causes and consequences, while visual mapping supported the articulation of relationships among organisational capacities, regulatory constraints, market incentives, and trust dynamics. This approach was particularly suited to an international, multilingual setting, where requiring formal CLD notation would have increased facilitation burden and reduced inclusiveness. Cycle 1 outputs were

synthesised through systematic qualitative analysis to produce a consolidated barrier structure ([MS5](#)), which served as the primary design input for Cycle 2.

The four participatory workshops took place in Italy (TCA), Greece (KEPKA), Iceland (LOKI Foods), and Hungary (KLT). Each workshop lasted approximately two and half hours and included an average of eight participants. These participants, which comprised food producers, food processors, retailers, cooperatives, marketing agencies, knowledge institutes, open market actors, associations, and standards organizations, were recruited through the networks of the case leads.

The workshops were recorded and subsequently transcribed using Microsoft Teams. The analysis was conducted based on both the full transcripts and the visual outputs generated during the sessions (through Miro or on papers). Combining these two sources allowed for a more comprehensive interpretation of workshop participants' perspectives and ensured that both verbal discussions and collectively produced visual insights were systematically incorporated into the analysis.

1.2.2 From Cycle 1 to Cycle 2: Synthesis and Design Preparation

Following Cycle 1, workshop outputs were consolidated to identify common barrier patterns across countries alongside context-specific differences. This synthesis marked a deliberate transition from problem diagnosis to intervention design, shifting the focus from identifying “what the problems are” to exploring how these problems could be addressed collectively at the value chain level.

The design of the Cycle 2 workshop protocol was informed by targeted desk research that translated diagnostic insights into concrete design orientations. First, WP2 deliverables ([D2.1](#) and [D2.2](#)) provided empirical evidence on the drivers and barriers of sustainable food choices, highlighting the importance of social norms, cultural context, trust, and communication credibility. WP2 findings showed that awareness alone is insufficient to change behaviour and that social aspects of sustainability are both highly relevant to consumers and difficult to measure and communicate. This evidence directly informed the decision to focus WP3 interventions on creating value from transparency, rather than on information provision alone. Second, the WP3 team conducted targeted desk research on international frameworks and standards, including FAO SAFA, ISO 26000, and Social Life Cycle Assessment approaches. These frameworks were used not as assessment tools, but as structuring references to help operationalise transparency-enabled sustainability in a way that could be meaningfully discussed with stakeholders and translated into communication and digital interventions. Together, this preparatory work shaped the structure and focus of the Cycle 2 co-creation workshop protocol.

1.2.3 Cycle 2 (2025): Co-Creation Workshop

In Cycle 2, the Ecosystem Pie Model (EPM) and Value Network Map (VNM) were embedded directly into the workshop protocol as integrated facilitation logics, rather than separate exercises. This integration was achieved using a Transparency Canvas (Figure 7: Transparency Canvas used at the co-creation workshop in 2025), a structured visual facilitation tool developed within WP3 to guide participants step by step from shared value articulation to concrete collaboration design. The Transparency Canvas structures the co-creation process into sequential mapping stages that support collective sense-making and design. It provides a common visual language that allows diverse stakeholders to jointly articulate

goals, roles, and relationships related to transparency, while ensuring comparability across countries and cases.

EPM logic was operationalised through the initial stages of the Transparency Canvas, where participants jointly articulated how transparency should create value for different beneficiary groups and translated this into a shared promise at the ecosystem level, clarifying who benefits and why collective action is needed. While VNM logic was embedded in the subsequent mapping stages of the Canvas, where participants identified key partners, the tangible and intangible resources they contribute, and the activities required to deliver the shared promise. By integrating EPM and VNM principles into accessible facilitation steps, the protocol ensured that system-level value creation and network configuration were jointly explored and translated into implementable intervention directions, while remaining practical and inclusive for diverse stakeholder groups across countries.

Throughout the development of the Cycle 2 protocol, the technology partner FINT was closely involved through continuous discussions with the WP3 research team (WU and TUE) to ensure that workshop outputs could be translated into implementable digital intervention directions.

During the workshops, FINT participated by presenting their existing digital infrastructure and field-level capabilities not as prescriptive solutions, but as illustrative building blocks to help participants understand what is technically feasible and to support informed co-creation.

The co-creation phase consisted of four in-person workshops in Italy (TCA), Greece (KEPKA), Iceland (LOKI Foods), and Hungary (KLT) designed to collaboratively develop and refine transparency-oriented intervention Scenarios across the food value chain. Each workshop had an average duration of approximately four hours and involved around seven participants representing a diverse range of stakeholders, including food producers, food processors, retailers, cooperatives, open market actors, marketing agencies, food authorities, associations, standards organizations, certification bodies, and chefs.

Following the workshops, the co-created outputs were further discussed with FINT to refine the Communication Toolkit, ensuring a balance between generalizable digital intervention logics and targeted technological components that could be adapted to different value-chain contexts.

Cycle 2 generated multiple sources of qualitative data, including participant-created artefacts produced during the Canvas exercises, facilitator notes, workshop recordings, and post-workshop reflections. These materials were analysed to identify recurring patterns in how co-created solutions addressed alignment challenges across the value chain, revealing key mechanisms such as shared value propositions, intermediary roles, and incentive structures, which form the core building blocks of the Communication Toolkit.

1.3 On the structure of the Toolkit: Awareness, Action and Aspiration

This Communication Toolkit offers a technological innovation that enables food value chain actors to communicate transparently with other industry stakeholders and consumers. These innovations are implemented through interventions in Business Models, using digital tools that enable transparency, traceability, and trustworthiness across the food value chain.

To ensure that interventions are carried out efficiently and successfully, this Communication Toolkit is structured according to the dynamic capabilities framework proposed by Teece (Teece, 2018). The

framework demonstrates how a Business Model becomes capable of organisational transformation, through possessing “dynamic capabilities”. “Dynamic capabilities” signify a “firm’s abilities to integrate, build and reconfigure internal competences” to address or, sometimes, bring about change (Teece, 2018). Within the dynamic capabilities framework, organisations sense opportunities and threats, seize them through resource allocation and mobilisation, and reconfigure structures, routines, and organisational culture to achieve timely and effective Business Model transformation.

Thus, drawing on this theoretical lens, we structure this Communication Toolkit (Figure 1: Structure overview of the Communication Toolkit) to provide strategic and efficient guidance for change, thereby enabling readers’ Awareness, Action, and Aspiration capabilities. In the “Awareness” section, we demonstrate how incorporating transparency practices into a Business Model benefits all actors within the food value chain. The “Action” section outlines effective intervention Scenarios to activate transparency, traceability, and trustworthiness across the food value chain and to achieve a desirable context-specific outcome. Lastly, the “Aspiration” section guides industry actors beyond their initial achievements and enables them to scale up the proposed innovation socially, organisationally, and institutionally.

Figure 1: Structure overview of the Communication Toolkit

Following consultation with the technology provider in the CUES project, it was agreed that, to ensure the long-term relevance of the Communication Toolkit in the context of rapid technological change and varying levels of infrastructure and resource availability in each context, digital solutions should be described at a functional and conceptual level rather than being tied to a specific technology or format. Accordingly, the Communication Toolkit outlines what the digital tool is intended to enable and how it should operate in practice, while allowing flexibility in its technical implementation. For instance, a solution that is currently realised as a widget may, with future technological developments, evolve into a different form without altering its underlying function.

2. Awareness

Screening widely for new business opportunities and being open to innovative interventions is a critical part of the innovation process (Linde et al., 2021). To help food industry actors evaluate the full potential of the proposed interventions and to prepare them for the implementation phase, we outline the value proposition of enhancing transparency within the food value chain.

The insights presented in this section are primarily grounded in desk-based research, complemented by empirical exploration conducted during the co-identification workshops. More specifically, the explanation provided in the Awareness component builds on prior master's thesis research, together with a critical analysis of business management and accounting literature, through the exploratory discussions held in the co-identification workshops, where participants reflected on transparency opportunities, challenges, and perceived benefits across different positions in the food value chain, which collectively informed the conceptual understanding of transparency-driven value creation.

2.1 Understanding Transparency

To comprehend the benefits of transparency, it is essential to first establish a shared understanding of the concept. Transparency emerged as a concept in response to the demand for higher standards of food quality, safety, and the sustainability of the production process (Trienekens et al., 2012). However, as consumer expectations grow, the requirements for “being transparent” have also become stricter (Schnackenberg & Tomlinson, 2016).

The concept of transparency was initially formulated as a process of information disclosure and was mainly treated as the company's accountability (Eijffinger & Geraats, 2006). From then on, transparency was viewed not only as a unidirectional mechanism of accountability but also as a multidimensional construct that enables trust-building. Therefore, to be transparent, information was required to not only be available but also accurate, clearly presented, and delivered in a timely manner (Schnackenberg & Tomlinson, 2016). However, not all information needs to be shared, but only what is substantial and relevant to stakeholders and consumers (Heimstädt, 2017). Otherwise, excessive sharing results in a lower level of understanding (Strathern, 2000).

The evolution has culminated in understanding transparency as a performative process. To fully embrace the value of transparency, businesses should regard it as an invitation to social action. Achieving transparency entails not only sharing topical, balanced information but also being receptive to ongoing dialogue. Unlike the straightforward, unilateral transparency of earlier times, contemporary transparency is a dynamic process that fosters negotiation and interpretation, thereby generating both value and unintended consequences, such as conflict or tension (Albu & Flyverbom, 2019). Openness to dialogue has thus become an inalienable dimension of transparency, in which negotiations of social aspects serve as a tool for transformational, social, and environmental change. Minding both the benefits and the unintended consequences of such open dialogue, food value chain actors can contribute to sustainable consumption while creating additional value within the food value chain.

2.2 Value of Transparency for Food Value Chain Actors and Consumers

2.2.1 Transparency as a Platform for Change

Transparency is crucial for empowering consumers to make more informed, conscious (Nuwarapaksha et al., 2024), and sustainable (Liu et al., 2023) food choices. Consumers' understanding of transparency has moved beyond merely providing certain information to seeing it as a platform for change, with social and environmental sustainability becoming a central driver of sustainable food choices. Alongside the call for more comprehensive labelling, consumers want to know whether societal injustices such as unfair working conditions, exploitation, and child labour are embedded in the production, processing, or distribution of food. The intention to be transparent in the production and labour conditions and to be socially and ecologically responsible to the communities that are involved in the food production process directly affects consumers' attitude towards an enterprise (Kang & Hustvedt, 2014). Thus, consumers perceive an opportunity to assess an industry actor's behaviour as a contribution to social and environmental improvement. Importantly, studies on factors influencing sustainable food choices have demonstrated that awareness alone is insufficient to affect a change in consumption patterns. The change must be accompanied by credible information, culturally resonant narratives, affordable and accessible options, and systemic support across the value chain (Van Prooijen et al., 2025).

In addition to delivering value from consumer interactions, transparency is also a business asset. Below, we outline how transparency becomes a financial, organisational, and relational value when embedded in a Business Model.

2.2.2 Financial and Market Value of Transparency

Transparency is a business asset. By establishing accountability, building trust and enabling businesses to implement sustainable, ethical and socially responsible practices, transparency can increase the competitiveness of a business in the food industry (CFDAS & DIAL Ventures, 2023; Schiefer, 2011). Moreover, disclosing environmental, social and governance data increases a company's financial value. The disclosed information can be viewed as additional non-financial information that guides investors' decisions (Yu et al., 2018).

2.2.3 Organisational Value of Transparency

Beyond increased market competitiveness, transparency benefits a company's organisational processes as shown in the study by Brockman et al. (2018). For example, it is easier to implement innovations in a Business Model when trust is established between industry actors and consumers. Such "societal trust" boosts innovation through established relational connections and facilitates long-term collaboration. Transparency facilitates innovation, particularly when industry actors are concerned about the opportunistic behaviour of potential partners or when formal contract enforcement is not possible (Brockman et al., 2018). Additionally, transparency improves the efficiency of fund allocation. Disclosing information about where funds come from, how a project is managed, and the project's details improves a company's efficiency. This benefit is particularly relevant for Non-governmental

Organisations (NGOs), as transparency reduces the risk of resource misuse, and thus increases an NGO's effectiveness in front of the public and donors (Rocha Valencia et al., 2014). Lastly, transparency increases trust between a company and its employees. When a company is open to public participation, shares relevant information, and is ready to public scrutiny, employees show a higher level of trust in the company's management and strategic direction, which leads to better a company's financial performance, labour productivity and product or service quality (Brown et al., 2015; Rawlins & Rawlins, 2008).

2.2.4 Relational Value of Transparency

Value creation is not a unidirectional process from the food industry to consumers. It is a dynamic process involving multiple relationships among actors in the food value chain, with each actor playing a role. For example, consumers' concerns about sustainability and social justice are addressed in the food value chain, and, in turn, an additional or new exchange value is created (Freudenreich et al., 2020). Transparency enables these relationships that are crucial to the value-creation process. Thus, transparency may be viewed as a tool enabling a co-creation experience between food industry actors and consumers, where consumers actively participate and shape the value of a product they are willing to pay for (Matarazzo et al., 2025; Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004).

2.3 Unintended Consequences for Producers and Businesses

As we have already mentioned, transparency is not a one-way flow of information from industry to consumers. It is a complex and dynamic process that entails both value creation and unintended consequences for an industry actor. These unintended consequences should be considered and strategically accounted for when deciding to implement a transformation towards transparency.

2.3.1 Administrative Burdens

Being transparent requires providing accurate comprehensive information regularly and in a timely manner, and engaging in ongoing dialogue with stakeholders, consumers, or the public, which may impose administrative burdens. For example, while bigger companies can cope with the increased financial and technical efforts to achieve transparency, it may be unbearable for small companies, which lack additional resources (Fifka & Loza Adai, 2015).

2.3.2 Transparency Paradox

In addition, companies may fall into the trap of a "transparency paradox" when applying transparency principles to employee management and labour performance tracking. When companies increase the observability of employees' everyday behaviour, it may reduce employees' work performance and encourage "hiding" behaviour (Bernstein, 2012). Similarly, transparency measures may be regarded by

a company's employees as intrusive when they disrupt professional work and induce pressure (Levay & Waks, 2009).

2.3.3 “Window Dressing”

Lastly, in pursuit of the values transparency offers, and in an attempt to meet ever-growing requirements of “being transparent”, a company may choose to report selectively, bend information to make it more representative, or orchestrate information for a particular audience. Such “window dressing”—presenting information to fit certain expectations—may indicate an inability to meet the ever-growing requirements for information disclosure, or a tactic to manage stakeholders and consumers’ impression of a company (Heimstädt, 2017).

KEY TAKEAWAY ON TRANSPARENCY

- The understanding of transparency has evolved from reporting to a complex performative process involving communication, negotiation and interpretation.
- Consumers view transparency as a platform for social and environmental change.
- Transparency creates financial, organisational and relational values for food value chain actors.
- Alongside these values, transparency entails unintended consequences, such as bureaucratic burdens, increased “hiding” behaviour or “window-dressing”.

3. Action

Once opportunities arising from transparency are identified, an innovative intervention to close the gap between reality and the desired scenario for transparent communication should be performed. However, in the early stages of implementing an innovation, multiple pathways are possible, and each step can be risky due to uncertainty (Teece, 2007).

To address this uncertainty, based on the co-creation workshops, three intervention Scenarios have been designed, including descriptions of the suitable actors, the context in which they apply, what is enabled by applying them, and the strategic considerations to keep in mind. Each Scenario aims to strengthen specific aspects of the food value chain in a particular context. Ultimately, the ideas derived from the workshops were complemented by desk research to support the validity of the proposed Scenarios and add explanatory and theoretical depth where necessary.

3.1 Achieving Desirable Scenarios through Interventions

Through four co-creation workshops in 2025, food industry actors from Italy (TCA), Greece (KEPKA), Iceland (LOKI Foods), and Hungary (KLT) shared their visions for empowering consumers to make sustainable choices and outlined how they would achieve this goal. As a result of these workshops, three intervention Scenarios have been designed, including descriptions of the suitable actors, the context in which they apply, what is enabled by applying them, and the strategic considerations to keep in mind. Each Scenario aims to strengthen specific aspects of the food value chain in a particular context. Ultimately, the ideas derived from the workshops were complemented by desk research to support the validity of the proposed Scenarios and add explanatory and theoretical depth where necessary.

Hereby, we present these Scenarios, with a detailed explanation of:

WHAT IS THIS SCENARIO?

A description of the intervention and what it aims to achieve.

WHO CAN USE THIS SCENARIO AS A STARTING POINT?

Signals to help assess whether this Scenario aligns with the current state of affairs of a food value chain actor.

WHAT DOES THE INTERVENTION ENABLE?

The possibilities that become available through intervention.

STRATEGIC CONSIDERATIONS

Key aspects to think about when implementing the intervention.

IMPLEMENTATION PATHWAY

A staged approach to integrating the intervention into the Business Model.

RECOMMENDATION

We recommend reading through all three Scenarios before deciding which approach best matches your needs. Many practitioners may find that elements of multiple Scenarios are relevant to their situation.

3.2 Scenario A: Trust Building among Short Food Value Chain Actors

3.2.1 What is Scenario A?

In many food value chains, actors operate in relative isolation from one another. Producers may have limited contact with processors, distributors may never interact with the farmers whose products they handle, and consumers remain entirely disconnected from the origins of their food. This fragmentation undermines trust and makes transparency and trustworthiness difficult to achieve.

The Scenario A “Trust Building among Short Food Value Chain Actors” uses a digital tool to strengthen connections across the short food value chain, thereby **building trust among food value chain actors and consumers**. If we imagine the value chain as a series of points connected by lines, this Scenario applies when linkages between actors are weak, and trust and coordination issues limit the potential for collaboration.

Figure 2: Scenario A, Trust Building among Short Food Value Chain Actors

This approach recognises that trust is built through interaction and visibility (Kraft et al., 2022). The proposed digital tool can reduce barriers to such interaction, enabling connections that would otherwise be impractical due to geographic distance, time constraints, or a lack of established channels.

The fundamental logic is simple: when actors can see each other and understand each other's work, trust grows. The digital tool can provide the infrastructure for this visibility without requiring actors to fundamentally change their core operations.

3.2.2 To Whom is Scenario A Applicable?

This Scenario is relevant if the following signals are recognisable:

ACTOR'S TYPE

- The actor is located in a short food value chain¹.
- Involvement in local agricultural production is a competitive advantage for the actor.

VALUES

- Value of transparency (e.g. financial, operational, relational) is sensed and defined.
- Transparency is seen as a way to maintain food quality and safety, as well as promote local development.
- Direct relationships with buyers and consumers are beneficial and highly valued.

VISIBILITY

- Sustainability practices (e.g. crop rotation, integrated pest management, improved irrigation efficiency) invested in a final product are not visible.
- Actors of the value chain are not aware of each other due to the lack of public visibility.

CHALLENGES

- Physical distance or logistical constraints prevent actors from building relationships.
- Digital barriers prevent an actor from building digital visibility (barriers to website building, social media profile maintenance, etc.)

3.2.3 What is Enabled through this Intervention and How?

An intervention oriented towards trust-building can enable the following possibilities:

ENHANCED VISIBILITY

The intervention aims to enhance farmers' visibility **by providing a lean, standardised, and user-friendly digital representation of local farms, improving visibility and building trust among farmers, retailers, and consumers.**

TRANSPARENCY FOR CONSUMERS

¹ According to Marsden et al. (2000) and Renting et al. (2003) a short food value chain as a supply arrangement in which consumers purchase products directly from the producer (e.g. farmer or processor) mostly through face-to-face interactions. This includes, for example, farm shops, farmers' markets, and street vendors, where direct contact between producers and consumers reduce the number of intermediaries and strengthen the connection between food origin, production practices, and consumption.

Such **uniform digital representations of local farms** allow consumers to track precisely where food was produced and which practices were used (e.g., pesticides, irrigation, crop rotation).

The key functionality of the associated digital tool:

MINIMUM EFFORT

Such a digital tool would require minimal or no data entry by connecting to existing databases (such as the [Agri-food Data Portal](#)). The retrieved data would be systematised and presented uniformly to produce a visual representation of a farm (including information on its location, size, soil conditions, and other related parameters).

PORTABLE DATA

Consequently, these visual representations of farms can be embedded on the existing websites of farmers, cooperatives or organic retailers to showcase where the products or raw materials are produced.

USER-FRIENDLY

Such a digital tool provides a user-friendly means of building a visual representation of different farms. It spares a farmer the need to hire a web designer, ensuring that information about the farm is available, systematised, and up to date.

ADDITIONAL DATA

If farmers wish to provide additional information about their farms or farming practices, it is possible to add it to the existing data retrieved from open databases.

3.2.4 Strategic Considerations

When approaching this Scenario, the following should be taken into consideration:

DEFINING BOUNDARIES BY ASSESSING THE DESIRED VISIBILITY

Transparency does not require revealing everything (Heimstädt, 2017). It is essential to consider which aspects of operations should be disclosed, what is topical and relevant for industry actors and consumers, and in what form it should be shared. The intervention should support operational boundaries, not break them. In the proposed digital tool, information about a farm will be retrieved from an open database in which farmers have already submitted data. Then, it is up to a farmer to decide what additional information would provide greater transparency and enhance visibility.

ASSESSING CAPACITY FOR ENGAGEMENT

Increased visibility may generate greater interest and more interaction requests. Consumers and industry stakeholders may begin engaging with the disclosed information, which requires timely, relevant responses. It is important to realistically consider how much engagement in dialogues or discussions can be sustained alongside primary operational activities.

IDENTIFYING THE PRIMARY AUDIENCE

Who is identified as the target audience in the short value chain? Would it be consumers, retailers or other local farmers? Different audiences may value different types of information. While consumers may be concerned with the health, environmental, and societal aspects revealed, farmers and agribusinesses may be interested in the technical nuances of sustainable business practices.

3.2.5 Implementation Pathway

Integrating the digital tool into a Business Model can be approached in three stages. This pathway provides guidance on what to expect and prepare at each stage.

STAGE 1: PREPARATION

WHAT TO ASSESS

- documentation and information which has already been shared as a part of routine operation (e.g. the information required to receive Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) subsidies);
- additional documentation or records available for sharing about business practices;
- digital platforms where a digital tool can be embedded as a widget² (websites, blogs, mobile applications, Facebook page etc.) or devices available (smartphone, computer, internet access);
- in case no digital platforms or digital tools are available, assess communications channels, where a link to the information about a farm can be shared (e.g. WhatsApp groups, local public web-portals);
- time available for the possible interaction with other actors due to the increased visibility;

WHAT TO PREPARE

- See what information has already been submitted to the public databases. If the information already submitted is satisfactory with respect to transparency, the data submission is complete.
- If the information from an open database is not enough to build transparency, identify 2-3 key practices or aspects of an operation which are not in the public databases. It could be information about sustainable farming practices, financial details, or strategic roadmaps that have not yet been made public.
- Discuss who will be responsible for managing the integration of the digital tool into the existing communication platforms and who will coordinate communication with internal stakeholders (retailers, consumers).
- Assess possible unintended consequences and risks which might follow (in cases like increased public engagement, increased bureaucratic burden, etc.)

² A small computer program, usually connected with an image, that can be added to a website to allow the user to do something. For example, you might click on a widget to find out weather or stock market information (Cambridge Dictionary, 2025).

 STAGE 2: GETTING STARTED**WHAT HAPPENS**

- Access the digital tool and familiarise yourself with its basic features (e.g. user interface, shareability, how easy it can be embedded into existing communication platforms).
- Check that the information provided about your farm or production facility is true and up-to-date.
- Keep in mind your target audience, with whom you want to establish trust. Think of what information your target audience is most interested in.
- In case more relevant transparency-enabling information should be displayed, make sure to submit this information.
- Assess the digital tool`s readiness to pilot:
 - Is the target audience clearly identified?
 - Is the information for the target audience relevant and complete?
 - Does the visual representation of a farm look lean and comprehensive?

EXPECTED CHANGES

- At this stage, changes are minimal, and the time is spent primarily learning about the system.
- No significant changes to core operations are required.

 STAGE 3: INTEGRATION**WHAT HAPPENS**

- The first results of the heightened visibility start appearing: the local public becomes aware of the local food producers. The first direct contact is established between local food producers, retailers, businesses, and consumers.
- The impact of the disclosed information starts being visible through the first interactions with the short value chain actors. For example, through interactions with retailers and consumers, it may become clear which information is most necessary, which is redundant, and what essential information is missing. When the patterns within disclosed information are analysed, addressing transparency gaps becomes part of a development strategy. Do “transparency gaps” represent a private zone of undisclosed information, or are they an attempt to construct a desirable image?

WHAT STRUCTURAL CHANGES HAVE BEEN MADE

- A successful pilot implementation of the digital tool has been achieved, and the tool is used as a reliable up-to-date visual representation of a farm.
- The habit of collecting and sharing information is achieved, and additional information is submitted to the digital platform when deemed necessary or beneficial.

- Gathering and digitising documentation becomes integrated into a process. For example, recording information about a harvested crop (harvest date, field, crop variety, fertiliser use) is not an afterthought, but an incorporated part of harvesting.
- Resource allocation and time investment stabilise, making an intervention viable for upscaling.
- Transparency-based visibility is heightened, and regular engagement with short food value chain actors yields collaborations, builds trust and facilitates creation of additional product value.

3.3 Scenario B: Collective Branding for Large Food Manufacturing Firms

3.3.1 What Is Scenario B?

Individual actors in the food value chain often struggle to communicate their practices effectively. A single producer claiming sustainability may lack credibility, and a lone processor defending against sector-wide criticism may go unheard. The challenge is not only a lack of visibility but also a lack of legitimacy for the individual voice.

The “Collective Branding for Large Food Manufacturing Firms” Scenario uses **a data platform with an incorporated AI Agent for coordinated communication and unified storytelling**. Rather than each actor broadcasting their own message independently, the intervention enables actors to present information collectively, creating a more comprehensive and credible picture of the sector or value chain.

Figure 3: Scenario B, Collective Branding for Large Food Manufacturing Firms

This Scenario shifts from a linear value-chain perspective to an ecosystem view, enabling ecosystem participants, including large manufacturing firms, **to contribute individually to a unified shared story**.

The agri-food industry is particularly vulnerable to disinformation and myths, including on such topics as GMO foods, food labelling, pesticide or palm oil use (Čechmánek, 2024). Thus, Scenario B also applies when myths, criticism, misconceptions, and disinformation affect consumers’ food choices. To combat

misinformation, collective unified storytelling enables coordinated responses that carry more weight than individual defences. When positive practices exist but are scattered and invisible, collective presentation aggregates them into a meaningful whole.

The fundamental logic is that telling one story amplifies credibility. While individual claims may be doubted, collective evidence from multiple independent actors forms a solid information source. **The data platform with an incorporated AI Agent is a proposed digital tool to synthesise credible information into a cohesive narrative** and debunk myths collectively, without requiring actors to surrender their individual identities.

3.3.2 To Whom is Scenario B Applicable?

This Scenario is relevant if the following signals are recognisable:

VALUES

- Using a unified story rather than separate individual stories would establish better communication across the food value chain.

CHALLENGES

- The agri-food sector is criticised for issues caused by some actors, even though the majority follow sustainable practices.
- Individual stories regarding the same topic are varied in the value chain.
- Individual communication efforts, such as sharing information through marketing channels, social media posts, or word-of-mouth, have limited reach or impact.
- Resources for communication are limited, making unified storytelling more influential.

POTENTIAL

- There is a desire to be publicly associated with the respected sustainable practices of other actors in the same industry sector.
- There is already an established networking organisation within the value chain that could aggregate individual stories, thoroughly verify them, feed them to the AI Agent, and offer a unified story for dissemination.

3.3.3 What is Enabled Through this Intervention and How?

An intervention oriented towards collective branding can enable the following possibilities:

SHARED UNIFIED STORY SYNTHESISED FROM INDIVIDUAL VOICES

The intervention requires contributions from multiple actors, creating a richer unified story than any individual could present alone. Each participant maintains their own voice while contributing to a collective narrative.

COORDINATED RESPONSE TO SECTOR ISSUES

When disinformation, misconceptions, or “conspiracy theories”, including AI-generated slop³ or hallucinations, flood the agri-food sector, the data platform with an integrated AI Agent can enable coordinated storytelling to collectively refute false claims. A network, where multiple actors provide consistent, evidence-based responses, carries more weight than isolated defences and can combat misinformation in the agri-food sector (Čechmánek, 2024).

VISIBILITY FOR NON-CONSUMER-FACING ACTORS

Actors who operate behind the scenes, such as suppliers, processors, and service providers, and their contributions⁴ to food sustainability can become visible through their contribution to collective storytelling, even if they have no direct consumer contact.

AGGREGATED EVIDENCE REFLECTING ACTORS’ DIVERSITY

While individual data points may seem insignificant, aggregated data across many actors can reveal sector-wide trends and commitment. Moreover, such aggregated data can be used to examine specific dynamics related to gender, age, and race of food value chain actors.

The key functionality of the data platform with an integrated AI Agent, the associated digital tool:

SYNTHESISING STORIES

The proposed data platform with an integrated AI Agent works as an aggregator of individual documented practices and stories. The data platform receives information from various sources, and the AI Agent synthesises a unified, cohesive narrative. The rumours and misinformation are identified and addressed in relation to the prevailing objective explanation, while the individual sustainable contributions of actors enhance the collective branding.

VERIFIED BY ORCHESTRATORS

To ensure the unified story is valid and accurate, the data platform’s input and the AI Agent’s output are verified by an orchestrator – an actor in the value chain responsible for networking and information dissemination. This prevents unreliable data from becoming part of the story, as well as AI slop and hallucinations.

INTEROPERABILITY ACROSS MULTIPLE SOURCES

The data platform supports manual uploads by an actor and automated data harvesting from sources defined by the actor (social media profiles, blog posts, websites, etc.), made possible by the platform’s interoperability.

ASSURING THE QUALITY OF THE UNIFIED MESSAGE

The data platform assessed by an AI Agent provides a comprehensive, trustworthy, unified narrative through content-aware, dynamic aggregation, analysis, and synthesis of data.

³ digital content of low quality that is produced usually in quantity by means of artificial intelligence (Merriam-Webster, 2025).

⁴ To mention a few examples of such contributions to the sustainability of the food value chain, food distributors optimise transportation, while retail actors collaborate with NGOs and take part in consumer education (León-Bravo et al., 2017).

3.3.4 Strategic Considerations

When approaching this Scenario, the following should be taken into consideration:

CLARIFY WHAT DISINFORMATION SHOULD BE CHALLENGED

It is important to identify what collective branding intends to challenge. False or harmful information in the agri-food industry may take different forms, such as⁵:

- *Fake news* – verifiably false, deceiving information. Example: “Scientists confirm that eating genetically modified corn causes cancer in humans.”
- *Rumors* – unverified information, which can be true or false. Example: “Farmers say a new pesticide ban is coming next year and crop yields will collapse.”
- *Misinformation* – unintentionally spread incorrect or misleading information with no harm intended. Example: “Organic food contains zero pesticides.”
- *Disinformation* – intentionally spread incorrect or misleading information with the intention to cause harm. Example: A coordinated online campaign falsely claims that imported wheat from a rival country is contaminated with heavy metals to disrupt trade.
- *Malinformation* – verified but taken out of context information with the intention to cause harm. Example: Sharing a real photo of a diseased animal from a single farm and claiming it represents the entire national meat supply.
- *Infodemics* – uncontrollable flow of true and false information during a pandemic. Example: Conflicting claims spread rapidly online about whether food packaging transmits COVID-19, whether certain foods “boost immunity,” and whether markets should close.

Thus, to combat any sort of deceiving or harmful information, it is important to understand why, how and by whom such information is produced, how it spreads (e.g. news, social media, WhatsApp chats, etc.) and what the consequences are. Taking all these factors into account helps you strategise the “debunking” process and understand with *whom* it should be done.

CLARIFY WHAT THE COLLECTIVE BRANDING STANDS FOR

Collective branding requires some agreement on:

- What participants understand by a “collective branding”. “Collective branding” may signify wider recognition of a generalised brand (such as Parmesan, Bordeaux, Colombian coffee), therefore boosting the association of individual members with higher quality and the collective brand’s reputation (Fishman et al., 2018). Alternatively, “collective branding” may be understood as a platform to emphasise stakeholder involvement, clarifying who the brand-authors are and how their stories contribute to the brand-narrative (Björner & Aronsson, 2022).
- What building a “collective branding” entails for the actors. Collective branding may serve as a regulatory tool, prescribing expectations and standards, or as a means to empower local voices and promote local identity (Gioia, 2025).

⁵ Definitions taken from Chowdhury et al. (Chowdhury et al., 2023)

- Who can be a part of collective branding? The entrance parameters should be outlined and discussed among the collective's actors and information orchestrators to adjust the desired level of exclusivity or inclusivity.
- What collective branding commitments are. Outlining individual commitments to the collective branding vision is necessary to coordinate individual efforts toward a shared promise.
- What are the actors' responsibilities in contributing to the collective voice? It is essential to outline the responsibilities of individual actors in developing collective branding.
- Who carries responsibility and who is accountable. Consider how to ensure that all participants contribute meaningfully to collective branding and meet its standards. Also, determine whether responsibility and accountability lie with a collective branding or an individual.

This need not be exhaustive, but there should be clarity regarding these core principles shared by all contributors.

BALANCE INDIVIDUAL AND COLLECTIVE IDENTITY

Contributors should benefit from the collective narrative while maintaining their individual identities. A digital tool should enhance rather than replace individual presence. This aspect should be considered when making decisions on entrance criteria, individual contributions, responsibility-sharing, and accountability mechanisms.

3.3.5 Implementation Pathway

Integrating the data platform with an integrated AI Agent for collective branding involves both individual preparation and coordination with others. This pathway provides guidance on what to expect at each stage.

STAGE 1: PREPARATION

WHAT TO ASSESS

- What practices are followed by an industry actor that can be used to aggregate or complement the collective story (sustainable farming, social advocacy, artisanal knowledge)?
- What types of false or harmful information (rumours, misinformation, etc.) are circulating around the agri-food sector? How can they be addressed by forming a unified story?
- How can this unified story contribute to achieving a shared promise (knowledge support, network support, resource sharing, myths busting)?
- What is the evidence or documentation of these practices (published and unpublished)?
- What network organisations or associations already exist, who could orchestrate the knowledge assembly, verification and dissemination?
- Who are the potential partners to consider building a collective branding with?

WHAT TO PREPARE

- To identify specific practices or commitments to form or contribute to a collective narrative and shared vision.
- To understand where these practices have already been mentioned (e.g. on social media, blogs, websites).
- To gather unpublished documentation that demonstrates these practices.
- Consider what type of false or harmful information regarding the agri-food sector would be beneficial to tackle. What would be an individual contribution to a collective branding, and what is expected from individual participation in a collective voice?
- Contact an existing networking organisation in the value chain (food collectives, marketing agencies, innovation hubs) that can become an orchestrator of the unified story creation via the data platform with an integrated AI Agent. To that end, compile a list of 5 actors to contact and begin outlining ideas for a potential collective branding and individual responsibilities.

▶ **STAGE 2: INITIAL USE**

WHAT HAPPENS

- In case the information about practices has already been published, share the sources with the data platform for the automatic data aggregation, analysis and synthesis.
- In case the information has not been published, share a story about one chosen topic with the data platform.
- Make sure your information and shared documentation are in alignment with the collective branding aims and/or shared visions.
- Begin to see how your contribution fits within the unified collective story.

WHAT CHANGES IN YOUR PROCEDURES

- Initial time investment to align your documentation with collective branding aims and/or narrative.
- You may need to adjust how you describe or categorise your practices.
- Core operations remain unchanged - the change is in how you communicate about them.

STAGE 3: INTEGRATION

WHAT HAPPENS

- Your participation in shaping the unified collective story becomes a regular part of your communication approach.
- You update your information periodically as your practices evolve.
- You may engage with collective activities, such as responding to sector issues, participating in shared initiatives.

WHAT STRUCTURAL CHANGES HAVE BEEN MADE

- Moderate adjustment: maintaining consistency with collective branding aims and/or narrative.
- Some coordination with other contributors to the collective branding may be needed periodically.
- Time investment depends on the level of collective activity.
- Some false and harmful information about the industry is tackled, and the renewed collective branding starts being acknowledged and recognised.
- Being a part of collective branding yields the first benefits, depending on the intention and desired outcome. If an individual actor desires to be publicly associated with the sustainable practices of other actors, the collective brand's reputation begins to benefit the individual actor. When the desire is to emphasise the impact of individual voices within the shared, unified narrative, the collective branding becomes stronger through added nuances that highlight what was previously unseen.

3.4 Scenario C: Empowerment of Small Food Producers

3.4.1 What is Scenario C?

Not all actors in agri-food value chains have equal resources, capabilities, or access to opportunities. Small-scale producers, actors in remote areas, those with limited technical infrastructure, and marginalised groups often face barriers that prevent them from participating in transparency initiatives, even when they have good practices to share.

The “Empowerment of Small Food Producers” Scenario uses a digital tool **to deliver targeted support to less-advantaged food producers**. Rather than assuming all participants start from the same position, this approach recognises that some actors need additional assistance to participate meaningfully in transparency systems.

Figure 4: Scenario C, Empowerment of Small Food Producers

This support takes multiple forms: **providing simplified tools that require minimal technical expertise; connecting actors to resources such as funding, knowledge, and training that they cannot easily access on their own; facilitating peer support and linking actors facing similar challenges; and improving visibility and access to markets.**

At the same time, the “supporters” benefit from the improved ecosystem, as more disadvantaged actors become potent and contribute to the viability, credibility and resilience of the food value chain. The common thread is reducing barriers that prevent capable actors from demonstrating their practices and establishing a viable, mutually beneficial ecosystem of actors.

Many actors are excluded from transparency systems not because they lack good practices, but because they lack the resources to document and communicate them. The digital tool addresses this gap.

3.4.2 To Whom Is Scenario C Applicable?

This Scenario is relevant if the following signals are recognisable:

ACTORS

- You are a small food producer.
- Sustainable practices are present, but the resources to document and/or communicate them are limited or lacking.

VALUES

- Farming practices would greatly benefit from consultancy and informed decision-making.
- Generated through the intervention data is considered an asset in terms of transparency and transparency-associated values.
- Sharing data is seen as a contribution to more efficient decision-making.
- Connecting with other actors, who face similar barriers and challenges, would be beneficial.

CHALLENGES

- Decision-making is often not possible due to the lack of knowledge or technical capabilities (measuring or digital tracking systems).
- There is no time, staff, or technical expertise to engage with complex digital systems.
- Most available digital tools seem to be designed for larger or better-resourced operations.
- Operational, financial or communication challenges persist, but it is unclear where to find relevant support or resources.
- There is a risk of being left behind as requirements for digitalisation increase.

3.4.3 What is Enabled Through this Intervention and How?

An intervention oriented towards empowerment through remote consultancy can enable the following possibilities:

SIMPLIFIED DOCUMENTATION

The intervention can provide digital tools to collect the necessary data to strengthen production, organisational, or communication capacities. This allows actors with limited capacity to produce records that meet market or regulatory expectations.

RESOURCE NAVIGATION

The intervention can help actors identify and access available support, such as consultancy, funding programs, technical assistance and training opportunities, that they may not know about or find difficult to navigate on their own.

PEER CONNECTION

The intervention can link actors facing similar challenges, enabling them to share experiences, solutions, and mutual support. Learning from peers who have solved similar problems is often more accessible than formal training.

The key functionality of the associated digital tool:

DATA MANAGEMENT AND VISUALISATION

The proposed digital tool offers data collection, management and analysis services. The information from the field (e.g. air temperature, soil humidity, solar radiation, etc.) is gathered by sensors. Consequently, advanced data management enables comprehensive environmental monitoring and informed decision-making (by a small farmer alone or with a remote consultant).

DATA COLLECTION FOR RISK CONTROL

Real-time, continuous data collection alerts a farmer when critical thresholds are reached or risks, such as disease outbreaks, are imminent, thereby optimising operations, reducing losses, and building farmers' resilience.

TURNING DATA INTO A BROADER ASSET

The collected, systemised, and visualised data is transferable and can be used for other purposes (e.g., applying for CAP subsidies or sharing the data to enhance a farm's transparency).

PROMOTING AND SUPPORTING SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES

Data collection enables management of water consumption, pesticide use, and productivity.

NO TECHNOLOGICAL BARRIERS

The digital tool is user-friendly and requires minimum efforts to enable data collection.

3.4.4 Strategic Considerations

When approaching this Scenario, the following should be taken into consideration:

IDENTIFICATION OF PRIMARY BARRIERS

Is the issue a lack of technical skills, insufficient information about support, peer isolation, or limited market access? Understanding specific barriers enables the intervention to address the most relevant challenges and request appropriate support.

START WITH WHAT IS MOST NEEDED

The intervention may offer multiple forms of support, simplified documentation tools, connections to funding and training, peer networks, and market visibility. It is not necessary to engage with all of these at once. It is important to begin with the support option that addresses the most pressing need.

FOCUS ON SUSTAINABILITY OVER COMPREHENSIVENESS

It is better to have a few key practices documented consistently, to maintain a few valuable peer connections, or pursue one funding opportunity thoroughly than to attempt everything at once. Having identified what matters most, it is important to proceed consistently.

EVALUATE SUPPORT RELEVANCE

If, during this intervention, an actor is provided with resources, training, or funding opportunities, it is essential to assess whether they are genuinely useful for the specific situation. Not all available support is relevant to all actors.

3.4.5 Implementation Pathway

Integrating the digital intervention when resources are limited requires a gradual, sustainable approach. This pathway is designed to minimise burden while building capacity over time.

STAGE 1: PREPARATION

WHAT TO ASSESS

- What are the most pressing constraints (time, technical skills, equipment, connectivity, knowledge gaps, market access)?
- What practices would be valuable to document or make visible?
- What decisions cannot be currently made due to the lack of knowledge or technical resources?
- What kind of support would be most helpful? Funding, training, technical assistance, peer advice, or connecting to markets?
- What actors in the industry face similar challenges who might benefit from a connection?

WHAT TO PREPARE

- Identify 1-2 practices that matter most to document, without trying to cover everything.
- If resource access is the priority: list the types of support you are seeking (knowledge sharing, funding, training, peer-to-peer consultancy, etc.).
- If help is the priority, formulate a question whose answer would allow you to make a decision.
- If peer connection is the priority, consider what challenges you would like to discuss with others.
- If market access is the priority, identify what you would like potential buyers to know about your operation.

STAGE 2: INITIAL USE

WHAT HAPPENS

- Access the digital tool and explore the features that are most relevant to the identified challenges.
- For resource access: explore what funding, training, or assistance is available.
- For peer connection: identify peers who face comparable challenges or have developed effective responses to shared problems.

- For market access: create a basic presence that reflects your operation.

WHAT CHANGES IN YOUR PROCEDURES

- Minimal: the goal is to become familiar with what is available.
- Time investment varies by entry point, but should be modest.
- Do not try to engage with everything at once.

STAGE 3: INTEGRATION

WHAT HAPPENS

- Your initial engagement with the digital tool becomes a regular practice, for example, digital documentation becomes an automated part of how you work.
- You may begin to use the collected visualised data for specific purposes (e.g. showing to buyers, applying for support).
- You may explore additional features of the digital tool as comfort grows.

WHAT STRUCTURAL CHANGES HAVE BEEN MADE

- The habit is established, time investment should feel manageable.
- You may consider expanding to additional dimensions/features if capacity allows.
- Resilience starts being established as the engagement with the digital tool progresses (e.g. through access to funding, knowledge, training, remote consultancy or critical condition(s) alarm).
- The establishment of data-collection practices starts yielding the first results. It becomes possible to establish transparent communication with the food supply chain actors.
- Thanks to thorough data management and analysis, more control over farming is gained. Thus, it becomes less risky to start implementing sustainable practices or make existing practices more sustainable.

3.5 Overview of Scenarios

The figure presents three complementary Scenarios within the Communication Toolkit. Scenario A: “Trust Building among Short Food Value Chain Actors” focuses on strengthening bilateral relationships among food value chain actors through transparent information exchange, dialogue, and reliability. The emphasis is on gradual confidence-building and reducing information asymmetries. Scenario B: “Collective Branding for Large Food Manufacturing Firms” moves from individual relationships to coordinated action, where multiple actors align around shared transparency standards and communicate a joint value proposition to consumers. Scenario C: “Empowerment of Small Food Producers” highlights a network-based scenario in which transparency tools enable actors, particularly smaller or less visible ones, to actively participate, influence decisions, and co-create value. Together, these Scenarios provide flexible pathways for advancing transparency in diverse agri-food contexts.

A: Trust Building among Short Food Value Chain Actors

Focus:

Strengthening connections between actors in the short value chain

Challenge addressed:

Lack of visibility and direct relationships between producers and other actors

B: Collective Branding for Large Food Manufacturing Firms

Focus:

Creating shared visibility and coordinated communication across the ecosystem

Challenges addressed:

Fragmented messaging and inability to address sector-wide issues collectively

C: Empowerment of Small Food Producers

Focus:

Targeted support for less-advantaged actors within the value chain

Challenges addressed:

Resource constraints, limited capacity, and barriers to participation in transparency initiatives

Table 3: Summary of the Scenarios

4. Aspiration

This section invites food value chain actors to look further and consider what becomes possible beyond initial implementation. How can engagement with a digital tool within an intervention deepen and expand? What collective activities might create impact beyond the proposed Scenarios?

The “Awareness” and “Action” sections of this toolkit address understanding and implementation, recognising the value of transparency and taking concrete steps to capture that value through digital interventions. Transparency in agri-food systems is not only about individual operations becoming more visible. Its full potential is realised when individual actions connect, aggregate, and contribute to broader systemic change across the institutional, intraregional, and international levels. This “Aspiration” section explores two dimensions of that potential:

DEEPENING AND EXTENDING THE INTERVENTION

How your engagement can deepen and expand over time, and how the three proposed Scenarios (“Trust Building among Short Food Value Chain Actors”, “Collective Branding for Large Food Manufacturing Firms”, “Empowerment of Small Food Producers”) can connect.

GOING BEYOND SCENARIOS

Going beyond local context, what agri-food value chain actors have envisioned doing together on an intraregional or international level to create change in the agri-food industry and establish transparency of the food value chain?

4.1 Deepening and Extending the Intervention

Once routine engagement with the intervention and the digital tool is established (Stage 3 in the “Implementation Pathway” sections), new possibilities emerge. This section consolidates the extension opportunities across all three Scenarios and explores how they connect.

4.1.1 Extending Scenario A: Trust Building

Once a transparent connection between industry actors has been established and trust has been built, the intervention extension might include:

EXTENDING THE TARGET AUDIENCE

Different audiences are interested in different information to be disclosed. Once trust has been established, it may be possible to broaden the target group. For example, at the beginning of the intervention, an organic food producer might benefit most from establishing trust with the nearest actors in the food value chain (e.g., food processors and packaging companies). However, targeting actors downstream in the supply chain (e.g., retailers) and outside the supply chain (e.g., customers, the general public) amplifies the relational value of transparency and enables more actors to participate in additional value creation (Schäfer, 2023).

DEEPENING RELATIONSHIPS

Having made initial contact and established trust, sustaining relationships with industry actors and customers is key. To ensure the actors' engagement, it is important to monitor that:

- All parties have equal access to information and knowledge.
- Misinformation does not hinder the relationship.
- Misunderstandings, personal values and beliefs (ethical commitments, cultural influences, personal convictions) are clearly expressed and considered.
- Social engagement and interactions are a part of communication (weekly markets, local fares etc.) (Warwick, 2025).

CONNECTING WITH PEERS

Linking with other actors using the same intervention can serve as a platform to share the ups and downs of implementation journeys, thereby creating a knowledge hub.

CONTRIBUTING TO TRUSTED INTERMEDIARIES

Trust established through transparency efforts is a foundation for the collective action described in Scenario B, "Collective Branding for Large Food Manufacturing Firms". A trusted, engaging, and sustained partnership is a starting point for establishing a collective voice (Figure 5: Scenarios' ecosystem, circular way of extending Scenarios).

4.1.2 Extending Scenario B: Collective Branding

In case of successful implementation of Scenario B with established collective branding as a result, the following pathways to expand the intervention are possible:

EXPANDING THE POOL OF CONTRIBUTORS TO THE COLLECTIVE BRANDING

Welcoming new members who share the collective branding commitments can be the next step to expand the intervention. To regulate the expansion process, it is advisable to assess the entry rules: do they permit expansion? Or would it be necessary to revise the parameters on who can contribute to the collective branding?

STRATEGIC TIP

When establishing rules for how a collective brand should be created, keep in mind that open entry and flexible choice of rules for a task at hand incentivise collective action more than closed entry and rigid choice of rules (Neef et al., 2023).

ADDRESSING NEW ISSUES

Extending the collective branding focus to additional sector challenges or opportunities can expand its potential. The spread of myths, rumours, and misinformation harms multiple aspects of the agri-food industry. It might be beneficial to address another layer of damage, such as assessing collateral damage when a specific product or process is targeted by false or harmful information.

TAKING ON COORDINATION ROLES

Commitment and leadership are crucial in building collective governance and orchestrating activities. Taking a leadership role and demonstrating individual commitment fosters an environment for growth, innovation and collaboration (Warwick, 2025).

ENGAGING IN POLICY DIALOGUE

The documented evidence of diverse practices, which, with the help of the AI Agent tool, shapes the unified narrative, can inform policy discussions and drive policy changes, as collectively established transparency can reveal shifts in the agri-food industry and emerging challenges.

SUPPORTING LESS-ADVANTAGED MEMBERS

Once a collective has been established, it is possible to consider helping actors with fewer resources participate fully, thereby entering Scenario C: “Empowerment of Small Food Producers” (see Figure 5: Scenarios’ ecosystem, circular way of extending Scenarios).

4.1.3 Extending Scenario C: Empowerment

If the basic barriers have been overcome and the initial capacities have been established, it is possible to consider the following:

PEER-TO-PEER SUPPORT

Once personal challenges have been addressed, actors can step into the “supporter” role and share their experience implementing the intervention with those at the beginning of the process.

STRENGTHENING MARKET POSITION

Once it becomes possible to establish a documentation and publishing routine, it is advisable to leverage improved transparency to access new services and markets (e.g., financial services and new selling venues).

JOINING COLLECTIVE EFFORTS

If it becomes clear that some challenges can be overcome only through collective effort, actors can leverage the capabilities gained and contribute to a collective branding, thereby moving to Scenario B: “Collective Branding for Large Food Manufacturing Firms” (see Figure 5: Scenarios’ ecosystem, circular way of extending Scenarios).

BUILDING DIRECT RELATIONSHIPS

Once the necessary operational and communication capabilities are established, transparency can be used to connect with buyers or consumers, thereby moving the intervention to Scenario A: “Trust Building among Short Food Value Chain Actors” (see Figure 5: Scenarios’ ecosystem, circular way of extending Scenarios).

Figure 5: Scenarios' ecosystem, circular way of extending Scenarios

4.2 Going Beyond Scenarios

Efforts to build transparency within the proposed Scenarios ecosystem (Figure 5: Scenarios' ecosystem, circular way of extending Scenarios), however successful, have limited potential. Collective action beyond proposed Scenarios, in which actors work together toward shared goals, is also essential to achieving systemic change and sustainable consumer behaviour.

Through eight problem co-identification and co-creation workshops across four European countries (Italy, Greece, Hungary, and Iceland), food value chain actors articulated what they would like to do together to create a broader impact. These collective activities are presented here not as a prescribed program, but as possibilities that your region, sector, or network might adapt and pursue.

In this section, we stratify these collective activities into three levels: coordinated engagement between agri-food value chain actors and consumers (B2C), coordinated engagement between agri-food value chain actors (B2B), and coordinated engagement between business and state structures (such as educational institutions) (B2G). Thus, in the following section, we propose three-layered collective activities (B2C, B2B, B2G) as an aspirational guideline (Figure 6: Layered structure of the proposed collective activities as an aspirational guideline for food value chain actors).

Figure 6: Layered structure of the proposed collective activities as an aspirational guideline for food value chain actors

4.2.1 Direct Consumer Engagement Activities

Connections enabled by transparency can be sustained by physical encounters. Workshop participants across countries emphasised the value of bringing consumers into direct contact with production. The possible types of activities may include:

CONSUMER VISITS TO PRODUCTION SITES

Organised visits where consumers can see production methods firsthand and communicate with producers directly, while a digital tool can facilitate coordination and booking (e.g. digital tool from Scenario A “Trust Building among Short Food Value Chain Actors” offers extensive information on farms to coordinate an event).

EVENTS TO PROMOTE LOCAL PRODUCTS

Open-air events, taste-testing opportunities, and festivals that showcase products from multiple producers. These create visibility and build connections with the local community.

INFORMATION DAYS FOR CONSUMERS

Interactive sessions with panels of stakeholders from across the food value chain. These sessions become a space for dialogue rather than one-way communication.

STRATEGIC CONSIDERATION

Physical events require resources and coordination. Start with what is feasible, even small-scale activities can build momentum for larger efforts.

4.2.2 Sustaining Collective Efforts

Collective activities require sustained individual commitment. Initial enthusiasm can fade, coordination costs can become burdensome, and free-rider problems can undermine participation. Workshop participants recognised the need for mechanisms to sustain collective efforts over time. For the sake of sustainability, it is important to consider the following:

ALIGN INCENTIVES WITH PARTICIPATION

Actors need to see ongoing benefit from their involvement. This might include access to shared resources, market advantages, cost savings, or reputation benefits.

DISTRIBUTE COORDINATION RESPONSIBILITIES

If coordination falls entirely on a few actors, they may burn out. Thus, it is crucial to share responsibilities across participants.

CREATE ACCOUNTABILITY MECHANISMS

In the case of individual contributions to a collective effort, it is crucial to develop clear accountability mechanisms (such as monitoring the process, clear reporting, and specifying who is accountable in the event of a crisis). These mechanisms will enable a collective to measure, monitor, analyse, and improve the performance of individual industry actors (Garton et al., 2022).

BUILD ON EXISTING STRUCTURES

It is advisable to integrate collective activities into existing organisations (cooperatives, associations, professional bodies) rather than creating entirely new structures.

CELEBRATE AND COMMUNICATE SUCCESSES

Visible achievements maintain motivation, attract new participants and become case-studies of successful innovation implementation.

4.2.3 Education and Knowledge Transfer

Transparency has a limited impact when consumers lack the knowledge to interpret and use the information provided. To turn transparency into value, food literacy education should be considered a collective investment. It involves:

SUPPORTING EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMMES

Addressing and guiding individual consumption behaviour is a necessary step, alongside systemic industrial, policy, and cultural changes, toward sustainable consumption. Implementing food literacy in educational programmes is an effective way to highlight the environmental and social impacts of the food industry and to connect with global and local food producers (Shepherd, 2025). Food literacy may include topics on:

- How to apply nutrition information.
- How to prepare healthy and flavourful food.
- How to trace the path of food through the food systems.
- How to understand the effects of food choices on the environment and economy.

COLLABORATING WITH EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Collaboration with educational institutions (e.g. schools, universities, and professional training programs) can help ensure the systemic implementation of food literacy education.

ACCESSIBLE INFORMATION

Limited consumer understanding of the benefits and mistrust of certifications and labels stem from a lack of awareness and insufficient knowledge (Nichifor et al., 2025). Creating accessible materials can help consumers understand what the communicated information means.

STRATEGIC CONSIDERATION: GREENWASHING AWARENESS

Although certifications and official labels may be trustworthy, broader greenwashing practices can undermine consumer trust in them (Hossain et al., 2025). This can be addressed by educational communication campaigns or programmes to raise awareness of greenwashing practices and the companies that engage in them (Álvarez-García & Sureda-Negre, 2023).

STRATEGIC CONSIDERATION: RESOURCE AWARENESS

Education is a long-term investment. Partner with organisations whose mission already includes education (schools, universities, consumer organisations, farm-school programmes) rather than trying to build educational capacity from scratch.

5. Closing Remarks

The aim of this deliverable was to create a Communication Toolkit that helps food value chain actors create and capture value through transparency efforts. Transparency should not be seen as an “add-on” communication activity, but as a strategic capability that can reshape relationships, incentives, and decision-making across the food value chain. Building on Teece’s framework (2018) and a multi-actor participatory approach, insights from the eight co-identification and co-creation workshops were translated into three core building blocks of the Toolkit: Awareness, Action, and Aspiration. The “Awareness” section shows how embedding transparency practices within Business Models can generate value for all stakeholders. The “Action” section presents practical, context-sensitive interventions that support the creation and capture of value through transparency. The “Aspiration” section encourages actors to build on early progress and scale transparency-driven innovations at social, organisational, and institutional levels.

This Communication Toolkit is designed for a broad range of food value chain actors; however, it is specific for each Scenario: In Scenario A, primary actors of the food value chain, such as farmers, smallholders, agricultural producers, livestock producers, NGOs, and consumer organisations and in general Producers in short food value chains, can more specifically apply this Scenario. In Scenario B, food value chain actors such as large food manufacturing firms, orchestrators, certifiers, and cooperatives may take on coordinating roles and apply Scenario B. In Scenario C, secondary actors of food value chains, such as technology providers, knowledge institutes, associations of small-scale producers, service providers, and NGOs, can directly enable primary actors' participation and engagement.

While the Communication Toolkit may not be directly applied in policy making, the “Action” section provides the context in which the policies should fit, and the “Aspiration” section indicates where the private and public sectors could act to enhance sustainable food consumption.

The central principle of this Communication Toolkit is that the three Scenarios are not linear stages but interconnected pathways within a dynamic ecosystem. Actors do not “complete” one Scenario and stop. Instead, engagement in one pathway may generate capabilities that facilitate movement toward another. Empowered actors (Scenario C) may develop sufficient capacity to join collective branding efforts (Scenario B). Collective branding initiatives (Scenario B) may strengthen individual trust-based relationships (Scenario A). Trust-building initiatives (Scenario A) may expose structural inequalities that require empowerment interventions (Scenario C).

This circular logic illustrates the evolving nature of transparency. As capabilities develop, relationships strengthen, and ecosystems mature, actors realign themselves within the transparency landscape. Therefore, the Communication Toolkit fosters adaptive reconfiguration, a key dynamic capability, rather than rigid implementation.

By combining the strategic value of transparency, context-based Scenarios, step-by-step guidance, and initial considerations for scaling, this Communication Toolkit offers a shared language and a practical starting point for making information more accessible, accurate, and timely. In turn, this can strengthen trust and support more sustainable food choices.

While the Communication Toolkit provides structured guidance, some limitations must be acknowledged: The Scenarios were co-developed in four European countries. Although generalisable principles were extracted, local regulatory environments, cultural norms, and infrastructural conditions

will influence implementation outcomes. Additionally, transparency interventions may be adopted symbolically rather than substantively. Without internal organisational alignment, there is a risk of greenwashing rather than genuine transformation. Recognising these limitations is essential to prevent unrealistic expectations and to encourage context-sensitive adaptation.

Finally:

*“ The journey of a thousand miles begins
with one first step. ”*

— Lao Tzu

6. Appendix

6.1 Transparency Canvas

Transparency	Industry Workers	Value chain partners	Local community	Society
Sub-category	Child & forced labour prevention	[Blue square] [Blue square] [Blue square]	Cultural heritage [Yellow square] [Yellow square] [Yellow square]	[Red square] [Red square] [Red square]
Example	agri-verification/auditing [Pink square]	[Green square] [Green square] [Pink square]	support festivals/museum [Pink square] [Green square] [Pink square]	[Green square] [Green square] [Green square]
Practical indicator to evaluate such effort	[Grey square]	[Grey square] [Grey square] [Grey square]	# of events funded [Grey square] [Grey square] [Grey square]	[Grey square] [Grey square] [Grey square]

Figure 7: Transparency Canvas used at the co-creation workshop in 2025

6.1.1 Canvas' Columns Description

COLUMN 1: INDUSTRY WORKERS

This covers all aspects related to the people who work directly in food production, processing, and distribution , etc.

COLUMN 2: VALUE CHAIN PARTNERS

This includes suppliers, distributors, retailers, marketing agencies, farmers' cooperatives, and other businesses that collaborate to bring food from farm to fork.

COLUMN 3: LOCAL COMMUNITY

This encompasses the broader community where food production and processing activities take place.

COLUMN 4: SOCIETY (INCLUDING CONSUMERS)

This represents our end-consumers and the public at large.

7. List of References

- Albu, O. B., & Flyverbom, M. (2019). Organizational Transparency: Conceptualizations, Conditions, and Consequences. *Business and Society*, 58(2), 268–297. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0007650316659851>
- Álvarez-García, O., & Sureda-Negre, J. (2023). Greenwashing and education: An evidence-based approach. *Journal of Environmental Education*, 54(4), 265–277. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2023.2238190>
- Astill, J., Dara, R. A., Campbell, M., Farber, J. M., Fraser, E. D. G., Sharif, S., & Yada, R. Y. (2019). Transparency in food supply chains: A review of enabling technology solutions. In *Trends in Food Science and Technology* (Vol. 91, pp. 240–247). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2019.07.024>
- Bernstein, E. S. (2012). The Transparency Paradox: A Role for Privacy in Organizational Learning and Operational Control. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 2(57), 181–216. <http://asq.sagepub.com>
- Björner, E., & Aronsson, L. (2022). Decentralised place branding through multiple authors and narratives: the collective branding of a small town in Sweden. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 38(13–14), 1587–1612. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0267257X.2022.2043415>
- Brockman, P., Khurana, I. K., & Zhong, R. (Irene). (2018). Societal trust and open innovation. *Research Policy*, 47(10), 2048–2065. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.07.010>
- Brown, S., Gray, D., McHardy, J., & Taylor, K. (2015). Employee trust and workplace performance. *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*, 116, 361–378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jebo.2015.05.001>
- Cambridge Dictionary. (2025). *Meaning of widget in English*. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/widget>
- Čechmánek, K. (2024). Disinformation, Misinformation and the Agri-Food Sector. *EU Agrarian Law*, 13(1), 21–27. <https://doi.org/10.2478/eual-2024-0003>
- CFDAS, & DIAL Ventures. (2023). *The Future of Traceability and Transparency in the Food System Market Opportunities*.
- Chowdhury, A., Kabir, K. H., Abdulai, A. R., & Alam, M. F. (2023). Systematic Review of Misinformation in Social and Online Media for the Development of an Analytical Framework for Agri-Food Sector. In *Sustainability (Switzerland)* (Vol. 15, Number 6). MDPI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15064753>
- Eijffinger, S. C. W., & Geraats, P. M. (2006). How transparent are central banks? *European Journal of Political Economy*, 22(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpoleco.2005.09.013>
- Fifka, M., & Loza Adauí, C. R. (2015). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Reporting—Administrative Burden or Competitive Advantage? In L. O’Riordan, P. Zmuda, & S. Heinemann (Eds.), *New Perspectives on Corporate Social Responsibility Locating the Missing Link* (FOM-Edition, Vol. 15). Springer Gabler. <https://doi.org/10.1007/9783658067946>

- Fishman, A., Finkelstein, I., Simhon, A., & Yacouel, N. (2018). Collective brands. *International Journal of Industrial Organization*, 59, 316–339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijindorg.2018.03.002>
- Freudenreich, B., Lüdeke-Freund, F., & Schaltegger, S. (2020). A Stakeholder Theory Perspective on Business Models: Value Creation for Sustainability. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 166(1), 3–18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-019-04112-z>
- Garton, K., Kraak, V., Fanzo, J., Sacks, G., Vandevijvere, S., Haddad, L., Brinsden, H., Laar, A., Karupaiah, T., Omidvar, N., Masters, W., Kauer, I., & Swinburn, B. (2022). A collective call to strengthen monitoring and evaluation efforts to support healthy and sustainable food systems: “The Accountability Pact.” *Public Health Nutrition*, 25(9), 2353–2357. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1368980022001173>
- Gioia, P. (2025). *Collective Place Branding Strategies in Rural Areas : Exploring Multi-Stakeholder, Cross-Sectoral, and Regulatory-Based Branding Initiatives for Enhancing Local Products* [Université de Toulon]. <https://theses.hal.science/tel-05073014v1>
- Heimstädt, M. (2017). Openwashing: A decoupling perspective on organizational transparency. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, (125), 77–86.
- Hossain, M. Z., Hossain, S., & Urme, U. N. (2025). The Impact of Greenwashing on Consumer Trust and Brand Loyalty: The Moderating Role of Industry Type. *European Journal of Innovative Studies and Sustainability*, 1(3), 121–133. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2025.1\(3\).10](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2025.1(3).10)
- Kang, J., & Hustvedt, G. (2014). Building Trust Between Consumers and Corporations: The Role of Consumer Perceptions of Transparency and Social Responsibility. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 125(2), 253–265. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-013-1916-7>
- Kraft, T., Valdés, L., & Zheng, Y. (2022). Consumer trust in social responsibility communications: The role of supply chain visibility. *Production and Operations Management*, 31(11), 4113–4130. <https://doi.org/10.1111/poms.13808>
- León-Bravo, V., Caniato, F., Caridi, M., & Johnsen, T. (2017). Collaboration for sustainability in the food supply chain: A multi-stage study in Italy. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 9(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9071253>
- Levy, C., & Waks, C. (2009). Professions and the pursuit of transparency in healthcare: Two cases of soft autonomy. *Organization Studies*, 30(5), 509–527. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0170840609104396>
- Linde, L., Sjödin, D., Parida, V., & Wincent, J. (2021). Dynamic capabilities for ecosystem orchestration A capability-based framework for smart city innovation initiatives. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.120614>
- Liu, Y., Heinberg, M., Huang, X., & Eisingerich, A. B. (2023). Building a competitive advantage based on transparency: When and why does transparency matter for corporate social responsibility? *Business Horizons*, 66(4), 517–527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2022.10.004>
- Marsden, T., Banks, J., & Bristow, G. (2000). Food supply chain approaches: Exploring their role in rural development. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 40(4), 424–438.
- Matarazzo, M., Oduro, S., & Gennaro, A. (2025). Stakeholder engagement for sustainable value co-creation: Evidence from made in Italy SMEs. *Business Ethics, the Environment and Responsibility*, 34(2), 347–361. <https://doi.org/10.1111/beer.12654>

- Merriam-Webster. (2025). *Slop*. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/slop#dictionary-entry-1>
- Neef, R., Busscher, T., Verweij, S., & Arts, J. (2023). How rule directions influence actors to achieve collective action: an analysis of Dutch collective infrastructure decision-making. *European Planning Studies*, 31(8), 1612–1633. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2022.2085030>
- Nichifor, B., Zait, L., & Timiras, L. (2025). Drivers, Barriers, and Innovations in Sustainable Food Consumption: A Systematic Literature Review. In *Sustainability (Switzerland)* (Vol. 17, Number 5). Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17052233>
- Nuwarapaksha, T. D., Udumann, S. S., Dissanayaka, N. S., & Atapattu, A. J. (2024). Leveraging Blockchain for Food Supply Transparency: From Farm to Fork. In *Emerging Trends in Food and Agribusiness Marketing* (pp. 75–100). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-6715-5.ch003>
- Prahalad, C. K., & Ramaswamy, V. (2004). Co-creation experiences: The next practice in value creation. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 18(3), 5–14. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dir.20015>
- Rawlins, B. R., & Rawlins, B. L. (2008). Measuring the relationship between organizational transparency and employee trust. In *Public Relations Journal* (Vol. 2, Number 2). <https://scholarsarchive.byu.edu/facpub/885>
- Renting, H., Marsden, T. K., & Banks, J. (2003). Understanding alternative food networks: Exploring the role of short food supply chains in rural development. *Environment and Planning A*, 35(3), 393–411.
- Rocha Valencia, L. A., Queiruga, D., & González-Benito, J. (2014). Relationship Between Transparency and Efficiency in the Allocation of Funds in Nongovernmental Development Organizations. *Voluntas*, 26(6), 2517–2535. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11266-014-9527-1>
- Schäfer, N. (2023). Making transparency transparent: a systematic literature review to define and frame supply chain transparency in the context of sustainability. *Management Review Quarterly*, 73(2), 579–604. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-021-00252-7>
- Schiefer, G. (2011). Available online at www.fooddynamics.org. In *Int. J. Food System Dynamics* (Vol. 2, Number 2). www.smartagrifood.eu
- Schnackenberg, A. K., & Tomlinson, E. C. (2016). Organizational transparency: A new perspective on managing trust in organization-stakeholder relationships. In *Journal of Management* (Vol. 42, Number 7).
- Shepherd, L. (2025). *Food Literacy Education: Conceptualization to Implementation*. Middle Tennessee State University.
- Strathern, M. (2000). The Tyranny of Transparency. *British Educational Research Journal - BR EDUC RES J*, 26, 309–321. <https://doi.org/10.1080/713651562>
- Teece, D. J. (2007). Explicating dynamic capabilities: The nature and microfoundations of (sustainable) enterprise performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 28(13), 1319–1350. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.640>

- Teece, D. J. (2018). Business models and dynamic capabilities. *Long Range Planning*, 51(1), 40–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2017.06.007>
- Trienekens, J. H., Wognum, P. M., Beulens, A. J. M., & Van Der Vorst, J. G. A. J. (2012). Transparency in complex dynamic food supply chains. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 26(1), 55–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2011.07.007>
- Van Prooijen, A.-M., Polyportis, A., Peiffer, L., De Keyzer, F., & Wang, Y. (2025). *Report on the social, economic and environmental factors that influence sustainable food choices.*
- Warwick, I. (2025). *Sustainability and Supplier Collaboration: A Path to Superior Service Quality in Italian Restaurants.* <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202502.1942.v1>
- Yu, E., Guo, Q., & Luu, V. (2018). ESG transparency and firm value. *Business Strategy and the Environment*.

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